

The Complex Formation between Cerium or Tungsten with Tartaric Acid in Alkaline Media.

BY R. RAMAN AND B. L. VAISHYA.

Walden (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2889) found that if uranyl salts are added to the active modifications of hydroxy acids, the optical rotation is changed and reaches a maximum, when the molecular proportions of the hydroxy compound to the salt is 1:1. This was afterwards studied by Grossmann and also by Darmois (*Compt. rend.*, 1923, 177, 49) who also came to the same conclusion and attributed this change to a complex formation. The effect of antimony, boric and arsenic oxides, on the optical rotation of tartaric acid was studied by Grossmann (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, 57, 533), that of the boric being recently re-investigated by Darmois (*Compt. rend.*, 1930, 190, 371). The effect of tin on tartaric acid has been investigated by Dumaski and Kniga (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 60, 220), that of hafnium and zirconium by Boer and Emmens (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1930, 49, 855), that of copper by Giuntini (*Compt. rend.*, 1930, 191, 778), and that of molybdic acid in alkaline media by Darmois (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 384; *compt. rend.*, 1923, 176, 1140). Recently the influence of thorium salts on the optical rotation of tartaric acid, and tartrates was undertaken by Darmois and Yen-ki-Heng (*compt. rend.*, 1932, 194, 703). All these workers came to the conclusion that a complex formation takes place in such cases. Henderson and Prentice (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 260) have observed considerable change in rotation when molybdic and tungstic oxides are dissolved in lactic acid and potassium lactate.

In this paper an attempt has been made to study the effect of cerium and tungsten salts on the optical rotation of tartaric acid in alkaline media and to see if some complex formation takes place. The same result was also verified by another independent method, that of noting the change in p_{H} values of the substance by *c. m. f.* method, using hydrogen electrode.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cerium Chloride and Sodium Tartrate.

Table I gives the results obtained with the polarimeter. It will be observed that the specific rotation goes on increasing with increasing amount of cerium chloride and reaches a maximum, when the solution contains 2 mols. of cerium chloride and 2 mols. of sodium tartrate. Following Henderson and Prentice (*loc. cit.*) $[\alpha]_D$ has been calculated from the formula

$$\frac{\alpha_D \times \text{vol. of solution}}{2 \cdot [\text{wt. of Na-tartrate and wt. of CeCl}_3]}$$

TABLE I.

Na-tartrate in 50. c. c.	CeCl ₃ added.	Corresponding wt. of Ce ₂ O ₃ .	Molar prop. Na-tart : Ce ₂ O ₃ .	α_D^{25} .	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.
0.26 g.	0	0	1 : 0	+ 0.30	+ 28.85
„	0.124 g.	0.055 g.	1 : 0.25	+ 0.60	+ 47.6
„	0.248	0.110	1 : 0.50	+ 0.80	+ 54.1
0.39	0.496	0.219	1 : 0.66	+ 1.80	+ 73.9
0.26	0.496	0.219	1 : 1	+ 1.20	+ 62.9
0.26	0.620	0.273	1 : 1.25	+ 1.20	+ 56.3

It was found that on diluting the solution there was no marked change in the specific rotation of the complex formed; but the temperature had an appreciable effect as is clear from Table II.

TABLE II.

Temp.	... 25°	40°	50°
α_D	... + 1.80	+ 1.90	+ 2.10
$[\alpha]_D$... + 73.9	+ 78.02	+ 86.3

Table III contains the results obtained by the *e. m. f.* method.

TABLE III.

Temperature = 18°.

Molar prop. of Na-tart : Ce ₂ O ₃	...	1 : 0·0	1 : 0·25	1 : 0·50	1 : 0·66	1 : 0·75
p _H	...	11·10	11·61	12·89	12·48	12·68

It is remarkable to find that *e. m. f.* observations also show a rapid change in the pH at the same place at which complex formation is observed with the polarimeter.

Cerium Nitrate and Sodium Tartrate.

TABLE IV.

Na-tartrate in 50 c.c.	Ce(NO ₃) ₂ added.	Corresponding wt. of Ce ₂ O ₃ .	Molar prop. Na-tart : Ce ₂ O ₃ .	α _D ²⁵	[α] _D ²⁵
1·941 g.	0·0	0	1 : 0	+2·35°	+30·3°
„	0·661 g.	0·250 g.	1 : 0·25	+2·70°	+30·8°
„	1·322	0·500	1 : 0·50	+3·95°	+40·1°
2·912	2·644	1·000	1 : 0·66	+7·55°	+48·3°
1·941	1·983	0·750	1 : 0·75	+5·10°	+47·4°

Effect of temperature on the optical rotation of the mixture at the compound formation is shown in Table V.

TABLE V.

Temp. ...	25°	40°	50°
α _D ...	+ 7·55°	+ 7·65°	+ 7·90°
[α] _D ...	+48· 3°	+48· 9°	+50· 5°

Table VI contains the results of *e. m. f.* measurements and p_H calculated.

TABLE VI.

Molar prop. Na-tart : Ce ₂ O ₃	...	1 : 0	1 : 0·25	1 : 0·50	1 : 0·66	1 : 0·75	1 : 1·00
p _H	...	13·07	13·24	13·26	13·31	13·32	13·93

It will be seen that *e. m. f.* measurements also show the complex formation at those concentrations at which polarimetric investigations also indicate the formation of complexes. In order to see if sodium nitrate has a depressing effect on the complex formed, the ratio of the complex formation with sodium tartrate and cerium chloride was taken with excess of alkali, 20 c.c. of *M/15*- NaNO_3 were added and the solution was made up to 100 c.c., the specific rotation observed was the same as that with sodium tartrate and cerium nitrate. On the other hand if 20 c.c. of *M/15*- NaCl were added to the complex formation between sodium tartrate and cerium nitrate, there was no effect, the specific rotation being the same.

Sodium Tungstate and Sodium Tartrate.

TABLE VII.

Na-tartrate in 50 c.c.	Na-tungs- tate added.	Molar proportion Na-tartrate : Na- tungstate.	α_D^{20} .	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$.
0.8879 g.	0	1 : 0	+0.50°	31.4°
	0.1650 g.	1 : 0.25	+0.75°	33.2°
	0.3300	1 : 0.50	+1.00°	35.6°
	0.4950	1 : 0.75	+1.00°	28.1°
	0.6600	1 : 1.00	+1.00°	24.0°

TABLE VIII.

Effect of temperature at the compound formation.

Temp.	...	20°	40°	50°
α_D	...	+ 1.00°	+ 1.30°	+ 1.40°
$[\alpha]_D$...	+ 36.6°	+ 45.0°	+ 48.6°

TABLE IX.

Results obtained by e.m.f. measurements.

Molar prop. Na-tart : Na-tungstate	...	1 : 0	1 : 0.25	1 : 0.50	1 : 0.75	1 : 1.00	
p_H calc. (Temp. = 18°)	12.42	11.89	11.59	11.89	11.86

The complex formation in this case is indicated at the same place as that observed by the optical method above.

Potassium Tungstate and Potassium Tartrate.

TABLE X.

K-tartrate in 100 c.c.	K ₂ WO ₄ added.	Molar prop. K-tart : K ₂ WO ₄ .	Temperature 20°			
			α_D^{20}	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	<i>e.m.f.</i> obs. (volts).	<i>p_H</i> calc.
0.4520 g.	0	1 : 0	+0.20°	+22.86°	-0.4074 × 2.036	8.2
	0.1630 g.	1 : 0.25	+0.50°	+40.64°	-0.4266	8.9
	0.3260	1 : 0.50	+0.95°	+61.05°	-0.5002	11.5
	0.4890	1 : 0.75	+0.951°	+50.23°	-0.4990	11.4
	0.6520	0 : 1.0	+0.95°	+42.06°	-0.4801	10.8

DISCUSSION.

Any compound formed by the interaction of the cerium or tungsten salt, with the normal alkali tartrate will be of the formula

where R represents the foreign substance and M, the sodium or potassium atom. This view is strongly held by Darmois (*Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1927, 36, 64) who describes the formation of such compounds or complexes and says that those which are stable in excess of alkali, combine with the alcoholic hydroxy group of the acid, thus forming the compounds of the tartar emetic type (Henderson and Baar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 542). It is observed from our work that when cerium nitrate or cerium chloride is added to an alkaline solution of tartaric acid, the optical rotation is increased and reaches a maximum, when the molecular proportions of cerium salt to tartrate is in the ratio of 2:3. It is probable that this change can only be due to the formation of new optically active compound or complex by the interaction of the inactive foreign substance and the active acid, the plausible formula of which appears to be on the basis of the views held by Darmois (*loc. cit.*) as $2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_3 : (\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6\text{M}_2)_3$.

In the case of the tungsten salt the maximum rotation is obtained when the solution contains 1 mol. of the tungstic acid and 2 mols. of the tartrate, the complex formed will have a formula as $\text{WO}_3 : (\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6\text{M}_2)_2$.

When we examined the various solutions by an *e.m.f.* method and calculated the *p_H* values, we found that at the same point as

indicated optically, there is a complex formation denoted by means of a rapid change in the p_H . It is remarkable that at the point of complex formation in the case of cerium chloride, the p_H value is maximum, while in the case of the tungstic acid it occurs at the minimum.

By comparing the results of Tables I and IV, it will be found that the specific rotation observed in the case of cerium chloride and sodium tartrate at the complex formation is higher than that obtained for cerium nitrate and sodium tartrate. If in these two cases, the complex formed is the same, the same specific rotation should be expected. The presence of neutral salts like NaCl and NaNO_3 , however, has some effect on the specific rotation of salts and esters of tartaric acid (Darmois, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 384; *Ann. physique*, 1928 10, 70). Darmois describes the negative effect of sodium chloride in the rotatory power of tartrate ion but has not investigated the effect due to sodium nitrate. Mallemann (*loc. cit.*) has described the effects of chlorides and nitrates of the alkali metals on the rotatory power of tartaric acid in aqueous solutions to be that of depression and is greater with the chlorides than with the nitrates. Our results obtained are in harmony with the views of Mallemann at least under the conditions of the experiment, using excess of the alkali.

SUMMARY.

1. The complex formation between sodium tartrate and cerium salts was studied in alkaline media by means of a polarimeter and potentiometer and it was found that a complex formation thus takes place when the molar proportions of sodium tartrate and cerium salt is 3:2.

2. The complex formation between alkali tartrate and tungstates was also studied in alkaline media. The complex formation in this case is with two molecules of tartrate and one molecule of tungstic trioxide.

3. It was observed that the p_H value of cerium salt complex is at a maximum, where it is also maximum for tungsten complex.

4. Specific rotation of the complex when cerium nitrate was used was found to be higher than that when cerium chloride was used.

Our thanks are due to Mr. Jang Bahadur Jha for his kind help in the case of *c.m.f.* measurements.